

Original Research Article

Strategies of Arabic Teachers in Preparing Students for the Knowledge Society through their Teaching Practices in Jordan

Dr. Jamal Abdel Fattah Al-Assaf*, Dr. Hanan Ismail Amaireh

Abstract

Applied University of Balqa University
of Jordan

*Corresponding Author's Email:
jamalassaf20032002@yahoo.com

The study aims to identify the strategies of Arabic teachers in preparing students for the knowledge society through their teaching practices in Jordan, as well as the relationship with variables: gender, scientific qualifications, and career experience. The sample of the study is taken from (206) male and female teachers, and the study tool is developed to achieve its objectives after reviewing the previous educational literature and studies. The results of the study presents that the most commonly used strategies are: activity-based instruction strategy, a performance-based assessment strategy, collaborative work strategy, respectively. The results of the study also show differences of statistically significance in teachers' strategies for preparing students for the knowledge society attributed to variables of: gender of male teachers, the scientific qualification for the teachers with a bachelor's degree, and the career experience for the benefit of the teachers with a career experience(5-10) years. The study provides a set of recommendations for further studies, other researchers could carry out in the future, such as create community-based training programs to develop teaching practices among Arabic teachers.

Keywords: Arabic teachers, knowledge Society, Pedagogical Practices

INTRODUCTION

Cognitive framework

Teaching is the bridge between individuals and society in all its sectors; it seeks to address ongoing cognitive, social, and economic changes; therefore teachers are required to be well-qualified and attentive in their ability to keep up with many of the changes and challenges ahead, and to maintain the trustship of all society members in this profession.

The teaching career must be adaptable in a rapidly changing society; all this can be achieved, only if teachers are able to energize students' intellectual abilities, develop their skills to adapt and work within the knowledge society (Coolahan, 2002).

Teachers must therefore develop teaching methods and strategies that satisfy students' cognitive needs, so that they become self-learners in the lights of the knowledge society principles, the main goal of the learning process must focus on coexistence with learning material using the best learning tools. As a result, learning is effective, rapid and accurate. With this regard, teachers should use variety of teaching methodology and strategies in order to make the sought change in students' abilities and intellectual skills. (Mosston and Ashworth, 2002)

Both of researchers believe that the knowledge society is primarily human-based; it is concerned about building, generating, and disseminating knowledge. It can

bring up to date the key structures of all sectors of society in all its respects; therefore, all countries should encourage distinctive innovative teaching; to become a distinctive qualitative knowledge society.

According to (Hargreaves, 2003), the requirements of building a knowledge society in teaching are:

- teach students according to the knowledge society; the priorities of teaching process in classroom are: building, reproducing, and applying knowledge.

- provide a safe, comfortable classroom environment for students supplied with all the modern technologies as the main resource of knowledge.

- encourage students to use creative thinking and critical thinking skills by motivating them to carry out higher-order mental processes while giving them learning tasks.

- develop instructional plans to achieve lifelong learning for students.

- encourage students to practice self-learning; through ongoing research of scientific knowledge.

- make teaching process less-effort with ease for students; by engaging them in classroom learning process.

- encourage students to engage in community participation; through open-mindedness to all different cultures of society.

- To motivate students and provide them with education and training of ICT; to prepare them to fully participate and be effective in the sought knowledge society.

The most prominent teaching strategies teachers should carry out within the classroom in line with the knowledge society are:

1- Strategy of teaching process Implementation: This requires setting the instructional topics to be presented in the classroom; where this information nature is up to date, challenging. In addition, it raises the potential of intellectual abilities, encourages them to use: higher-order thinking skills, creative thinking, and critical skills. In fact, such process requires teachers to stimulate student awareness; by motivating students to use multiple resources while accessing data and information; so that the process takes into account to: students' abilities by providing learning content that is based primarily on brevity, complexity through solving the learning task, coherence when presenting ideas, and appropriate learning activities during resolving the learning concepts (Espoito, 1999), in addition to teachers' effort sought to use modern technology while presenting information to students in the classroom (Munro, 2010).

2—critical-thinking teaching strategy: Teaching based on critical thinking processes relies on further than learning the basic skills of science tasks; it goes beyond using advanced intellectual processes when learning any educational task (Lemov, 2010). The fact that critical thinking processes have a direct connection to problem-solving skills; teachers should provide advanced, non-static, and taken for granted learning tasks. Moreover, these tasks should have more than one explanation for

their truth and scientific truth, as well as encourage students to employ certain skills: analysis, synthesis, and assessment, to address multiple learning problems (Lemov, 2010).

3-- Problem-Solving and Inquiry Strategies: (Bingham, 2004), problem-solving strategies are structured around developing students' cognitive, social, and emotional skills to enable them to effectively solve educational problems that face them; in which developing these skills helps students to adapt not only to the classroom environment but also to their daily lives in the shades of knowledge society, (Aarenofsky, 2001). As a result, teachers should concentrate directly on the students' central role in solving the educational problem. Encourage students to carry out more knowledge strategies when solving any learning problem, monitor students and guide them constantly.

4- Collaborative Work Strategy: (Louis et al., 2004), this strategy simply means dividing students into small, heterogeneous groups of learning abilities to: encourage positively interact with each other, enhance interaction, and integrate into other students, exchange of knowledge experiences.

Although many studies prove the effectiveness of this method in pre-school students, the use of collaborative work strategy with students at all levels of school has a positive impact on increasing motivation: for high academic performance, to learning process, as well as enhancing confidence in many abilities. Moreover, such strategy can be employed on brainstorming to be effective in accessing knowledge when students are divided into groups, but unfortunately, it is more often used when the number of students per class is relatively small.

5-- Activity-Based Instruction Strategy: This strategy is based on the training of students in the practical application of different educational tasks, particularly the recent ones, by encouraging students to: employ various educational tools of educational tasks, use multiple resources to access information; So that students become constantly eager to access knowledge from modern technological sources such as the Internet, computers, and smart phone devices, to satisfy their cognitive needs. As a result, this contribution makes the entire process of classroom learning modern, developed, and up-to-date to cope with the demands of the modern age. (Milkova, 2008).

6—Performance-Based Assessment Strategy: This strategy requires students to demonstrate their learning by employing self-skills in real-life situations, or ones that simulate real situations, such as performance-based assessment, talking, presentation, role play (Abu Khalifa et al., 2011). Teachers are strongly required to teach using this strategy in the lights of the knowledge society by: identifying student performance levels, creating appropriate student assessment rubrics, and engaging students in the classroom assessment process.

Most studies have focused, in particular, on teacher roles in the lights of the knowledge society, while few studies about teaching strategies of Arab language teachers based on the knowledge society are rarely found, according to the knowledge of both researchers. Perhaps, it may be useful to mention some of these studies that address study variables of: teachers and the knowledge society's terminology.

With reference to (The ISABDA and Atisabda, 2015) study, it aims to develop teaching models, professional practices in order to prepare teachers for teaching based on the knowledge society. Regarding this purpose, the study develops models based on: education technology, education technology based on developed curricula, and employment of teaching technology by teachers in classroom. In fact, all models, mentioned earlier, are based on the knowledge society. Both researchers used the qualitative approach building upon the method of focused groups through data collection.

The results of the study show the effectiveness of previously used teaching methodology based on the knowledge society in classroom teaching, in general; which is pointed out according to both researchers to constantly train teachers in teaching strategies based on the knowledge society before joining the teaching process.

Another study, (The Blandul study, 2015) aims to see how teachers use teaching strategies based on innovation as a prerequisite for Romanian knowledge society based on: teaching methods, using modern teaching methods, employing modern assessment methods. The sample of the study consisted of (158) individuals who responded to a questionnaire made up of (20) multiple choice items in which the results of the study indicated that the highest arithmetic mean were respectively for teachers: use of teaching strategies based on the knowledge society, use of modern teaching strategies, use of assessment techniques, and use modern devices to teach which is the least computational averages.

Moreover, in (Vali, 2013) study, the researcher seeks to learn the teachers awareness of employing teaching strategies based on knowledge society in Romania. The sample of the study consisted of (26) male and female teachers who are asked: to agree/ disagree of using teaching strategies based on the knowledge society in teaching. In addition, teachers are asked to demonstrate the benefit of using technology in education to access data and information about academic content. The results of the study indicated that (0.73) teachers consider it viable to employ teaching strategies based on knowledge society as well as the use of technology in education helps students to access to knowledge and thus generate knowledge to gain greater benefit from information.

Further study is conducted by Al-Qaeili and Al-Hanan (2013) to formulate a vision for developing the competencies of teachers of Arabic language and history

in lights of knowledge society demands and their attitudes toward its application. The sample of the study consists of (60) male and female teachers El Kharga Educational Administration schools in New Valley governorate in Egypt. Both researchers developed a note card and a measurement of trends toward the requirements of the knowledge age, which demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed program in developing teachers' competencies against the knowledge society, as well as statistically significant differences in the trend scale between the prior application and thereafter application of the proposed training.

(Maren, 2013) design is to train teachers to teach in the lights of the knowledge society, of which a training program of knowledge society model is created. The study sample consists of (22) teachers through a process of: a pre-questionnaire, training program, post survey. The results of the study showed that there are statistically significant differences between prior training and after training, goes into the after training. As a result, the study demonstrates the effectiveness of the knowledge society based on training program.

Other studies like (Plump and Zamfir, 2011) aims to develop the skills of teachers in teaching methods based on the knowledge society in Romania, where a sample of (158) undergraduate students, the researcher refers to the phrase "renewable energy may help to develop our lives". The researchers follows the analysis, dialogue and discussion method which aims at developing critical and creative thinking skills as teaching strategies based on the knowledge society. Later, the students are trained, the researchers applies a questionnaire to evaluate the used teaching methods. The results of the study demonstrated the effectiveness of teaching methods used to develop critical and creative thinking skills as a teaching strategy based on the knowledge society.

In 2007, (Shadefat, 2007) conducted a study aims at identifying to what extent primary school teachers, in Directorate of Education-Mafraq, "practice of knowledge Economy Competencies". The study shows that (3.69) mean average is extent of use of knowledge Economy Competencies arithmetic mean. The study draws a scale of ranks: first, personal competencies, second, technical competencies, third, measurement and evaluation competencies, fourth, the efficiency of ICT, and the last rank, the competencies of professional growth. The results of the study also indicated no statistically significant differences attributed to gender, experience and the scientific qualifications of primary school administrators.

After reviewing previous literature studies, the following can be drawn:

– Many of the previous studies emphasizes on the effectiveness of teaching based on the knowledge society, its role in developing the human component -- student, and the need to transform into the foundations of the knowledge society, such as the study of (Blandul,

2015) and (Vali, 2013). In addition, the study of AL-Qaeili and AL-Hanan (2013), which clearly indicates the importance of teaching based on the principles of the knowledge society.

– Many previous studies emphasizes on the need: to build design models in line with knowledge society, to train teachers in teaching with regard to knowledge society, such as the study of (Atisabda, 2015) and (Maren, 2013), which emphasizes on the importance of teacher training in teaching on the basis of the principles and foundation of the knowledge society.

Both researchers, takes into considerations in lights of the above studies, formulate the study purpose, unlike previous studies, teaching strategies based on knowledge society focusing on Arabic language teachers through studying the effect of variables like: gender, qualification, career experience.

Down to earth guidance, teachers face many obstacles in carrying out teaching strategies based on knowledge society; for, no clear vision of the concepts related to the knowledge society, the lack of training on teaching strategies to transform to teaching strategies based on knowledge society, in addition, the lack of pedagogical literature content of studies related to teaching strategies based on knowledge society and its connection to students and teachers; according to both researchers and their best knowledge.

2. The problem of study

Teacher is considered the main pillar in the process of development and modernization made by the Ministry of Education, in light of the development of the educational curricula in accordance with the standards and educational requirements of the knowledge society, which gives priority to research and follow-up the need to monitor the teachers reality in the education field. This can be done through: the awareness and practice of teachers' role, teaching strategies, and the professional and cognitive content that must possess. Right up to build students' personality required to be global citizenship rather than local, which live up to access knowledge by: understanding, generating, and practicing through these strategies. At this respect, researchers find it an intellectual challenge through practice in the educational fields, in an attempt to uncover the teachers' performance weaknesses according to the educational guidance of the knowledge society for the teaching strategies implemented in actual field. Therefore, this study intends to identify the pedagogical practices of the strategies of Arabic language teachers in preparing students for the knowledge society by answering the following questions:

1-- What instructional strategies do Arabic language teachers practice in preparing students for the knowledge society?

2-- Are there statistically significant differences in the teaching strategies practiced by Arabic language tea-

chers in preparing students for the knowledge society due to variables: gender, scientific qualifications, and career experience?

The importance of the study

This study takes its significance for:

- This study is important for its subject matter; learning about pedagogical strategies based on the knowledge society's vision of Arabic teachers is most important issue in teachers' pedagogical practices.
- This study contributes to the development of methods to improve the teaching process in its real field, and may encourage supervisors to re-assess teaching strategies with students.
- The study can help empower curriculum practitioners and help decision makers to learn about the teaching strategies of Arabic language teachers, which contributes to future educational policies in this area.

Objectives of the study

The current study aims to:

- 1—identify the most important instructional strategies do Arabic language teachers practice in preparing students for the knowledge society.
- 2—find out if there are differences in the level of instructional strategies teachers' use that are attributed to (gender, scientific qualification, and career experience).

Study terms

The knowledge society: The society that guides its members toward accessing, participating in, using, and creating knowledge, under the umbrella of improving the quality of life in all its fields, through the use of a rich information service, advanced technological applications, using the human mind as a capital, and employing scientific research. The procedural definition is a collection of behaviors, actions, and activities that the teacher practices in the classroom that enable teacher to deal accurately and skillfully with knowledge: employing, disseminating, and generating, in order to effectively employ them in all areas of life for learners.

– **instructional practices:** It is the classroom teacher conduct, behavior and activities, including: teaching strategies, teaching methods, tools, media used by the teacher to present material content, methods of presenting material, primary and sub-goals of the teaching process, teacher's methods to accomplish these goals. The procedural definition lies in the extent of which teachers access the scale created by the current study.

Table 1. The study population and sample according to variables: gender, scientific qualifications, and career -experience

	Scientific Qualification of teacher	Career Experience				Gender		
		Less than 5	5-10	More than 10	Total	Male	Female	Total
Level	Bachelor	67	53	35	155	65	90	155
	Master & higher	25	15	11	51	30	21	51
	sum	92	68	46	206	95	111	206

– **Strategy:** All educational tools, educational styles, pedagogical styles, and educational tactics used by Arabic teachers to achieve the desired objectives of the classroom learning process (Bingham, 2004).

Study limits and Delimitations

This study is determined by:

- Human limits: Arabic language teachers at the university's district schools in the capital Amman.
- Time limits: The study is carried out during the first quarter of the 2019/2020 school year.
- Spatial limits: The university's' district schools in the capital Amman.
- Study limitations: The results of this study are determined by the psychometric connotations of the study's two tools as well as the sincerity and objectivity of the study's individual response.

METHOD AND PROCEDURES

This study aims to learn how Arabic teachers use teaching strategy based on knowledge society through teaching practices. To achieve this goal, this study is conducted from a range of methods and procedures including methodology, sample, tool, procedures, and statistical methods used to answer study questions.

Study methodology: Researchers used the quantitative approach by using the descriptive method of studies that is appropriate to the nature, objectives, and questions of this study.

The study population and sample: The current study population is made up of all (412) Arabic language male and female teachers in Amman, through the use of the stratified random sample method and (206) male and female teachers which is (%50) from the study population. The following random sample equation is carried out: (sample/population x 206); taking account to teacher gender, research selects (95) male teachers, (111) female teachers randomly marked from the study

population, and Table (1) shows the sample and variables of the study:

Study tool

A scale is developed to measure the use of Arabic language teachers for teaching strategies based on knowledge society through teaching practices; reference is made to theoretical framework and relevant previous studies, such as the studies of both, AL-Qaeili and Hanan (2013), and Shadifat (2007). The validity of the scale is confirmed by finding signs of sincerity and stability in the following ways:

Honesty: Virtual truthfulness is applied by presenting the scale's statements in their initial form to (10) arbitrators, with competence in the field of Arabic language teaching methods, curricula, and educational psychology. Each arbitrator is asked to give an opinion on the scale statements based on standards of: the relevance of the statements to the study dimension, the clarity of the language of the statements, the use of appropriate language in formulating statements with regard to Jordanian Cultural environment, and the function of the statements to measure.

All arbitrators recommend certain modification on the scale with respect to standards: the relevance of the statements to the study dimension, on statements language. Therefore, arbitrators' suggestions are made to all the scale statements, five statements are deleted from the strategy for implementing the teaching process. As a result, the number of scale statements is (58) statements in last form.

Building validity: Building-validity indicators are confirmed by calculating Pearson's association transactions between the scale paragraphs and the scores of each field. A survey sample of (30) teachers – other than sample of the study- is carried out to find out the correlation coefficients between paragraph results and each dimension of the scale. (As Table 2 shows).

Notes from table (2): The coefficients relevance with the domain ranged between (0.467 -0.835) and the scale between (0.286-0.781), passes the criterion for

Table 2. Values of the correlation coefficients between the scale paragraphs and the degree of each of its fields

Dimension	Paragraph number	The content of Paragraphs According to Areas	Relevant to:		
			Dimension	Scale	
Teaching Implementation Strategy	1	Make sure to communicate with my student to facilitate their learning and cognitive development.	0.809**	0.750**	
	2	Make to guide students toward continuous learning and provide them with books and research.	0.585**	0.546**	
	3	Motivate and support students' ideas and suggestions.	0.787**	0.725**	
	4	Use appropriate learning resources.	0.677**	0.623**	
	5	Employ learning techniques in the teaching and learning processes.	0.739**	0.645**	
	6	Create supportive and motivational learning environment.	0.539**	0.489**	
	7	Use appropriate educational strategies to students' abilities.	0.626**	0.670**	
	8	Encourage students to present and discuss their ideas.	0.777**	0.680**	
	9	Give students adequate time to respond to the activities.	0.733**	0.676**	
Critical Thinking-Instruction Strategy	10	Develop students' critical and creative thinking skills.	0.572**	0.533**	
	11	Analyze scientific findings to critical issues and concepts.	0.799**	0.710**	
	12	Practice students with analysis, assessment, and self-assessment skills.	0.742**	0.669**	
	13	Guide Student not to take for granted information.	0.777**	0.706**	
	14	Model strategies by thinking aloud.	0.679**	0.630**	
	15	Use logic and scientific evidence to judge ideas.	0.710**	0.659**	
	16	Guide students to uncover strengths and weaknesses of certain arguments	0.720**	0.655**	
	17	Use graphs, maps, charts, and visual organizers for students.	0.756**	0.685**	
	18	Monitor student progress to give feedback if needed.	0.658**	0.612**	
Problem-Solving and Inquiry Strategies	19	Identify the initial outcomes which students earn as a result of their research practice.	0.634**	0.607**	
	20	Put into practice principles and foundations of problem-solving and inquiry strategy in teaching.	0.715**	0.637**	
	21	Maintain students' role in problem-solving.	0.762**	0.691**	
	22	Organize the time to provide training of problem-solving and inquiry.	0.607**	0.562**	
	23	Direct and guide students in identifying the required knowledge resources.	0.517**	0.443**	
	24	Support and encourage students as needed during Strategy implementation.	0.740**	0.697**	
	25	Guide students to use different methods of problem solving.	0.723**	0.696**	
	26	Monitor student results using appropriate assessment strategies and standard records.	0.482**	0.306**	
Group work Strategy	27	Plan to work in groups.	0.786**	0.777**	
	28	Divide students into homogeneous or heterogeneous groups based on educational situations.	0.726**	0.676**	
	29	Monitor the work of groups by roaming around and listening to their discussion.	0.713**	0.678**	
	30	Re-arrange the educational environment so that groups can work easily.	0.467**	0.286**	
	31	Teach students the positive behavior for group work.	0.755**	0.740**	
	32	Support and Encourage collaboration and teamwork among students.	0.731**	0.680**	
	33	Respect and accept students' points of view.	0.719**	0.676**	
	34	Train students to practice leadership, and communication skills with others.	0.485**	0.307**	
Activitybased strategies	Instruction	35	Choose appropriate activities for students taking into account individual differences.	0.665**	0.675**

Table 2. Continue

	36	Use activities to drive and engage students' learning.	0.792**	0.755**
	37	Use instances related to strategies line to Lesson.	0.673**	0.624**
	38	Provide more real life activities to urge and increase students' curiosity.	0.826**	0.761**
	39	Enhance student autonomy to self-learning	0.797**	0.772**
	40	Use available resources at school to carry out the strategy.	0.772**	0.736**
	41	Give students the opportunity to show their presentations.	0.656**	0.614**
	42	Monitor the outcomes using assessment strategies and standards related to activity itself.	0.793**	0.733**
Performance-based Assessment Strategy	43	Identify the purpose of the assessment clearly	0.768**	0.745**
	44	Create a list of skills required to present to students.	0.767**	0.735**
	45	Describe performance of observed behaviors.	0.621**	0.553**
	46	Select tables of Performance indicators.	0.731**	0.654**
	47	Select tables of performance levels.	0.712**	0.670**
	48	Select the assessment tool.	0.773**	0.748**
	49	Describe the performance in qualitative style.	0.643**	0.588**
	50	Give students feedback of their performance development.	0.792**	0.732**
	51	Collect information about Student performance and provide verbal descriptions.	0.835**	0.781**
	52	Observe and Follow-up the students performance in different situations.	0.753**	0.723**
	53	Provide Immediate feedback to students through direct observation.	0.633**	0.577**
	54	Choose educational situations appropriate for abilities, desires, and preferences of students by using observation.	0.740**	0.693**
	55	Encourage students to write their notes on their private learning-log.	0.810**	0.758**
	56	Keep student learning-log.	0.750**	0.713**
	57	Discuss with students their observations and reflections in light of their achievements	0.616**	0.559**
	58	Follow up student learning-logs.	0.660**	0.600**

*D at an indication level of 0.05

**D at Level of significance 0.01

confirming the paragraph – must be more than (0.20) -. Therefore, all the scale paragraphs with a correlation coefficient above 0.20 are confirmed. No scale paragraph is deleted.

The scale, as it is final form, consists of (58) paragraphs divided in the following dimensions:

1—after the implementation of the teaching strategy: (9) paragraphs, (1–9).

2—after the critical-Thinking Teaching Strategy: (9) items, items 10–18.

3—after the problem-solving and investigation strategy: (8) items, paragraphs of (19-26).

4- after the collective Action Strategy: (8) paragraphs, paragraphs of (27-34).

5—after the activity-based instruction strategy: (8) items, items (35–42).

6—after a performance-based assessment strategy: (16) paragraphs (43–58).

Reliability: Reliability of the gauge is verified in two ways:

Reliability by repetition: The Reliability of the scale of Arabic language teachers using the teaching strategies based on knowledge society is confirmed after applying it to (30) students other than the original study sample, Reliability is calculated in a two-week interval between carrying out the scale two times, with regard to use the Pearson correlation coefficient which is (0.93) whole scale. In addition, the stability of variable for the scale sub-dimensions is formulated in the following table:

From the previous table, the researcher concludes that the values of stability by repetition of each dimension of the scale of Arabic language teachers' use of the teaching strategies based on knowledge society through their teaching practices ranged from (0.90-0.72), which are statistically functional values, indicating that the scale dimensions, and the scale as a whole, have appropriate stability values.

Stability of internal consistency: To learn about the alpha- Lee Cronbach values of the scale of Arabic

Table 3. Coefficient of Stability in repetition of the scale of Arabic language teachers' use of the teaching strategies based on knowledge society through their teaching practices

Dimension	Stability Coefficient	Stability Coefficient	Number of paragraphs
1	Implementation strategy Teaching process	0.72	9
2	Critical thinking strategy	0.90	9
3	problem-solving and inquiry strategy	0.77	8
4	Collaborative work strategy	0.88	8
5	Activity based teaching strategy	0.75	8
6	Performance-based assessment strategy	0.78	16
Overall scale stability		0.93	58

language teachers' use of the teaching strategies based on knowledge society through their teaching practices, the stability coefficient reapplied for each dimension of the scale, and for the overall degree as shown in Table 4.

From the previous table, the researcher concludes that the values of Alpha- Lee Cronbach of each dimension of the scale of Arabic language teachers' use of the teaching strategies based on knowledge society through their teaching practices ranged from (0.90-0.72), and are confirmed since all values of alpha- Lee Cronbach are statistically functional values.

Variables

Gender: it has two levels (male and female).--

--Scientific qualification: it has two levels (Bachelor, Master and higher)

Teaching experience: It has three levels (less than 5 years, 5-10 years, and more than 10 years)

Study tool Affirmation: Both researchers use the statistical standard to judge the of the arithmetic mean average of paragraphs as follows: first, Low average (1 - 2.33), second, medium average (2.33-3.66), third, high average (3.67-5.00).

Data Analysis: To answer the study questions, the data in the scale is drawn and analyzed statistically using the Statistical Program (SPSS); where appropriate statistical methods is used to answer each study question as follows:

*To answer question 1: Arithmetic mean, standard deviations, and the relative importance are used of studying the extent of the use of Arabic language teachers for a knowledge society-based teaching strategy.

*To answer question 2: Three-Way Analysis of Variance (3-Way ANOVA) without interactions is used to examine whether there are statistically significant differences in teachers' strategies in preparing students for the

knowledge society attributed to variables: Teacher's gender, scientific qualifications, and career experience.

RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The study aims to identify the strategies of Arabic teachers in preparing students for the knowledge society through their teaching practices in Jordan, from the perspective of the teachers, as well as the relationship with gender variables, scientific qualifications, and career experience. Answers for the questions of the study are:

To answer question 1, which states, "What instructional strategies do Arabic language teachers practice in preparing students for the knowledge society?" the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the dimensions of the study tool are used, as illustrated in table 5.

Table 5 demonstrates that averages for teacher-use teaching strategies based on knowledge society through their teaching practices ranged from (3.10-3.98), the Activity-based Teaching Strategy takes the highest rank for the fifth dimension with an arithmetic mean of (3.98) and a high degree. Then, a performance-based assessment strategy comes in the second rank for the sixth dimension with an arithmetic mean of (3.77) and a high degree, last but not least, a problem-solving and inquiry strategy with an arithmetic mean of (3.10) and a high degree. Moreover, the entire average "for teachers using the teaching strategy based on the knowledge society through their teaching practices" is (3.54) with medium level.

To answer the second question, which states, "Are there statistically significant differences in the teaching strategies practiced by Arabic language teachers in preparing students for the knowledge society due to variables: gender, scientific qualifications, and career experience??"the arithmetic mean and standard deviations of the sample individuals scores are set on the instructional strategies practiced by Arabic language teachers in preparing students toward the knowledge society based on the study variables, as demonstrated in the table (6).

Table 4. Coefficient of Internal consistency of sub-dimensions of the Arabic language teachers' use of the knowledge society-based teaching strategy through their teaching practices

Dimension	Coefficient of LeeCronbach	Number of paragraphs
Implementation strategy Teaching process	0.70	9
Critical thinking strategy	0.77	9
problem-solving and inquiry strategy	0.76	8
Collaborative work strategy	0.79	8
Activity based teaching strategy	0.81	8
Performance-based assessment strategy	0.75	16
Overall	0.85	58

Table 5. Arithmetic mean and standard deviations of the dimensions of the teachers' use of teaching strategies based on knowledge society through their teaching practices, with their dimensions descending according to their averages among student.

Dimension Number	Rank	The medium strategic	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Level
5	1	Implementation strategy Teaching process	3.98	0.754	High
6	2	Critical thinking strategy	3.77	0.823	High
4	3	problem-solving and inquiry strategy	3.68	0.757	High
1	4	Collaborative work strategy	3.37	0.425	Medium
2	5	Activity based teaching strategy	3.35	0.484	Medium
3	6	Performance-based assessment strategy	3.10	0.616	Medium
Overall scale stability			3.54	0.324	Medium

Table 6. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of sample scores on instructional strategies practiced by Arabic language teachers in preparing students toward the knowledge society based on study variables.

Variables	Category	Arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation
Gender	Male	3.54	.656
	Female	3.32	.435
Scientific Qualification	Bachelor	3.66	.588
	Master and higher	3.16	.654
Career Experience	Less than 5 years	3.53	.742
	5-10 years	3.66	.680
	More than 10 years	3.25	.571

Table 6 shows the significant differences between the sample' arithmetic means at of the entire average of teaching strategies practiced by Arabic language teachers in preparing students for the knowledge society, in light of the distribution based on study variables. To test the significance of these differences, Three-Way Analysis of Variance (3-Way ANOVA) without interactions. Table 7 summarizes the results.

Table 7 shows that:

1--There are statistically significant differences ($\alpha=0.05$) in the overall average of teaching strategies practiced by Arabic language teachers in preparing students toward a society of knowledge based on gender variable which

are attributed to the benefit of males.

2-- There are statistically significant differences ($\alpha=0.05$) in the overall average of teaching strategies practiced by Arabic language teachers in preparing students toward a society of knowledge based on scientific qualification variable which are attributed to the benefit of the Bachelor's degree holders.

3- There are statistically significant differences ($\alpha=0.05$) in the overall average of teaching strategies practiced by Arabic language teachers in preparing students toward a society of knowledge based on career experience variable which are attributed to the benefit of (5-10) years experienced teachers.

Table 7. Three-Way Analysis of Variance (3-Way ANOVA) without interactions of sample' arithmetic means at of the overall average of teaching strategies practiced by Arabic language teachers in preparing students for the knowledge society, in light of the distribution based on study variables.

Source of Variance	Sum of squares (SS)	Degrees of freedom	Mean squares (MS)	F Calculated	Statistical significance
Gender	2.412	1	2.412	8.522	*.004
Scientific Qualification	10.366	1	10.366	36.629	*.000
Career Experience	8.457	2	4.229	14.943	*.000
Error	56.882	201			
Total	2608.050	205			

Significance Level (Alpha) α = 0.05

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the first question indicated that the activity-based teaching strategy dimension comes in the first ranked in practice, which clearly points out that Arabic language teachers encourage their students to use motivational and self-learning-enhancing activities during teaching practices. The results goes in line to (Vali,2013)study, which emphasized the importance of using technology to endogenously build, generate students' knowledge. In addition, the results are also consistent with(Hargreaves, 2003) study which mentions that teaching students based on knowledge society requires the teacher to encourage students to recognize ones' self and self-esteem-through the learning process--by encouraging students to self-confidence during knowledge acquisition. As a result, there is a need to emphasize on the importance of guiding the educational performance of Arabic language teachers toward self-confidence-building, encouraging students to self-learning strategy –of which both researchers consider one of the training approaches that teachers receive in the Ministry of Education's training programs - focusing mainly on students' self-learning as well as to avoiding teachers as a major source of information as much as possible, this encourages students to self-accessing data and information, and discussing with classroom colleagues.

In the second rank, comes performance-based assessment, this clearly demonstrates: the importance of the assessment process for Arabic language teachers, the clarity of purpose of the whole process. This result goes with the findings of (Blandul, 2015) study, which emphasizes the importance of the assessment process during teaching students.

The collaborative-work strategy takes the third rank. It is a clear indication that Arabic language teachers followed the group teaching style with students, which is consistent with finding of (Kember and Leung, 2005)study which emphasizes on the importance of the collaborative work strategy in the teaching of students.

In the last rank, come the problem-solving and inquiry

strategies, which indicate that the problem-solving method is poorly used in mental processes through processing information in teachers' practices; as teachers employ no principles of this strategy in teaching. The researchers believe that Arabic language teachers receive training courses in a more detailed, systematic, and focused manner to use and practice principles and strategic foundations for problem-solving and inquiry in classroom teaching.

The results of the second question indicate the statistically significant differences in variables: gender, scientific qualifications, and career experience of teacher strategies in preparing students toward the knowledge society are for the benefit of Arabic male teachers, Arabic bachelor's degree teachers, and Arabic language teachers with career experience (5-10 years).

The underlying reason –according to both researchers explanation- is the harmony with the gender roles of both males and females, as females take the family role and household responsibilities which makes the new strategies serious obstacle to be carried out. The results of this question indicated that the teachers of Arabic who have a Bachelor of scientific qualification are more interested in teaching strategies based on the knowledge society through their teaching practices. The results also indicated that Arabic language teachers with career experience (5-10 years) are more interested teachers in teaching strategies based on the knowledge society through their teaching practices. This suggests that Arabic language teachers with somewhat new experience have more awareness than others of the importance of teaching strategies based on the knowledge society and their role in developing students' higher cognitive competencies. This leads to the recent studying of university academic courses that teacher engaged in universities practical experiences of which: certainly guide to the concepts in the study variables throughout putting in practice modern, developed strategies in teaching. In addition, teachers' desire is to achieve their academic self-realization in the educational field, since it is hard to get an educational job position with respect to difficult economic conditions of the country.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers recommend conducting the following studies:

- 1- develop specialized training programs to employ educational techniques through the practices of Arabic teachers.
- 2- Study the role of teaching strategies based on knowledge society in developing higher-order thinking skills of students.
- 3- Study of employing the problem-solving and inquiry strategy in classroom teaching of Arabic teachers.
- 4- Study of the teaching strategies of Arabic language teachers in light of the knowledge society from the perspective of the students.

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